

Figure 1 - Differences in aboveground dry biomass (a-b) and relative biomass (c-d) between control and biochar treatment in January 2023 (a and c; after the start of grass tillering) and April 2023 (b and d; at the peak of flowering and biomass development). Yellow dots represent estimated marginal means and yellow lines their confidence intervals.

Figure 2 - The percentage change in species responses to biochar-amended soil at peak of biomass development (April 2023), based on estimated marginal means extracted from robust linear mixed effects models (left plots) and belonging t-values overlaid with Hedge's g effect sizes based on residual standard deviations from random intercepts (right plots). Blue columns represent t-values and red lines represent Hedge's g values. Right Y axes representing Hedge's g are mirrored (i.e. set with positive values in both directions) as Hedge's g is always positive; a – biomass responses; a and b- relative biomass responses; c and d – relative biomass responses; e and f – counts responses; g and h – relative counts responses; i and j – vigor responses

Figure 3 – Smooth modeled Renyi diversity profiles of pasture community in control and biochar treatment at peak of biomass development (April 2023) using natural splines; a – count-based diversity profiles and b – biomass-based diversity profiles. Shaded areas represent confidence intervals, whereas circle symbols on the lines are set on α -levels of 0, 1, and 2; representing richness, Shannon effective species number, and Simpson effective species number cut-offs on the diversity curve, respectively. F-statistic and corresponding p-values represent the global effect of biochar treatment on the diversity profile shapes of pasture community composition.

Figure 4 – Species richness and count-based differences in diversity indices between control and 4% biochar treatment at peak of biomass development (April 2023), based on estimated marginal means from the LME models; a) estimated mean number of species, b) Shannon-Weiner index – uncertainty of prediction to which species will a randomly selected plant in a community belong, c) Pielou's evenness – evenness (distribution) of species relative abundances in a community, d) Gini-Simpson index – probability that two random plants in a community will belong to different species, e) and f) Simpson and Shannon diversity, respectively – number of species in equivalent community with the same diversity index value (Simpson and Shannon index, respectively), but with completely even species abundances.

Figure 5 – Biomass-based differences in diversity indices between control and 4% biochar treatment at peak of biomass development (April 2023), based on estimated marginal means from the LME models; a) estimated mean number of species, b) Shannon-Weiner index – uncertainty of prediction to which species will a randomly selected plant in a community belong, c) Pielou's evenness – evenness (distribution) of species relative abundances in a community, d) Gini-Simpson index – probability that two random plants in a community will belong to different species, e) and f) Simpson and Shannon diversity, respectively – number of species in equivalent community with the same diversity index value (Simpson and Shannon index, respectively), but with completely even species abundances.

Figure 1

Seed mixture species

Figure 2

Figure 3

Smooth modeled diversity profiles

Figure 4

Count-based diversity metrics

Figure 5

Biomass-based diversity metrics

